

AutoVision

User Guide

Introduction to AutoVision

Basics

AutoVision is a digital tool that links autonomous vehicle characteristics with possible long-term impacts, looking ahead about 30 years into the future. It focuses on highly automated autonomous vehicles, which are classified as level 4 and 5 on the international SAE scale.

Principle

The AutoVision tool is based on two scientific models developed to link autonomous vehicle characteristics with impacts:

- **Study-Method-Impact (SMI):** This model links autonomous vehicle usages (such as working or sleeping in the vehicle) to qualitative social impacts (such as decreased health status or improved social relationships). It is based on expert opinions from sociologists, urban planners, ergonomists, and others.
- **Representation-Usage-Impact (RUI):** This model links autonomous vehicle deployment characteristics (such as whether the vehicle is shared and the geographic area in which it operates) to socio-economic and environmental quantitative impacts (such as average speed or CO2 consumption). It is based on scientific studies.

Attention! These two models are not connected to each other. This means that a usage is not linked to any socio-economic or

environmental impact, or that no mode of use is linked to a social impact. It is important to keep this in mind when using the tool.

Modes

The tool offers two distinct usage modes, each identified by a specific color code.

- **Advisor mode (orange).** This mode involves defining a strategy for the autonomous vehicle, specifying the desired impacts or not. The tool then provides a list of suggestions to help create a concept of an autonomous vehicle that aligns with the chosen strategy.

- **Impact Guesser mode (purple).** This mode involves defining a concept of an autonomous vehicle, which includes providing a set of characteristics such as vehicle usage or mode of use. The tool then generates a list of probable impacts categorized by themes.

Advisor mode

Principle

If you don't have a specific idea for an autonomous vehicle concept and want suggestions or ideas, you can use the Advisor mode. This tool calculates suggestions that match a strategy you have defined.

Accessing the Advisor Mode

To access the Advisor Mode, click on the orange button located below the sentence: "What impacts do you want your concepts to cause/avoid?"

Navigation in Advisor mode

The Advisor mode consists of two pages.

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- The Strategy page where you can define your strategy
- The Advices page where the tool calculates suggestions for your autonomous vehicle

The image displays two overlapping screenshots of the AutoVision 1.7 Strategy page. The top screenshot shows the 'Social impacts' section, and the bottom screenshot shows the 'Socio-economic and environmental impacts' section. Both sections feature a table with columns for 'Indicator' and 'Trend'.

Social impacts

List of Impacts

Indicator	Trend
Social interactions	
Changes in accident responsibility	
Access to mobility	↑
Number of employees in the delivery sector	
Number of accidents	
Health condition	
Substance consumption	↓
Number of vehicle thefts	
Working time	
Capacity / sense of direction	

Socio-economic and environmental impacts

List of Impacts

Indicateur d'impact	Trend
Space required for vehicles	
Mileage per vehicle	
Travel time	
Capacity at intersections	↑
Parking space required	
Slowdown at intersections	
Total mileage	↓
CO2 emissions	
Average speed	
Energy consumption	
Total number of taxis	
Total number of vehicles	↑
Mileage per person	
Total number of vehicles on the road	
Capacity for merging lanes	
Fuel consumption	
Greenhouse gas emissions	
Road capacity	

Defining a Strategy

When you are on the strategy page, you can define your preferences regarding the impacts you want or don't want. A complete list of impacts is provided, and for each of them, you can:

- Indicate that you want this impact to occur (↑)
- Indicate that you want to avoid this impact (↓)
- Not express any preference (nothing)

Calculating Advice

Once you have defined your strategy, simply click on the "CALCULATE ADVICE" button located at the bottom-right corner of the page to calculate your advices.

The screenshot shows the 'AutoVision 1.7 / Strategy / Advices' interface. It features two main sections: 'Usages' and 'Continents'. Each section has a 'To promote' and 'To avoid' toggle. The 'Usages' section displays a table with 5 rows of usage items, each with an 'Experts' count, a 'Conflict' percentage, and a list of 'Impacts'. The 'Continents' section displays a table with 4 rows of continent entries, each with a 'Description', 'Studies' count, and 'Conflict' percentage.

Usages

To promote: Usages for which experts give trends that on average align with your selection.
 To avoid: Usages for which experts give trends that on average oppose to your selection.

☑ To promote ☑ To avoid

Usage	Experts	Conflict	Impacts
⚠ The passenger travels long distances despite being temporarily unable to drive	3	76%	Substance consumption ↑, Access to mobility ↑
⚠ The passenger is a minor and travels long distances	3	46%	Risk of kidnapping ↑, Quality of family ties ↓, Quality of family ties ↑
⚠ The passenger does not know where they are going	2	83%	Access to mobility ↑, Risk of kidnapping ↑
⚠ The vehicle finds a parking spot and parks there without a passenger	1	0%	Access to mobility ↓
⚠ The passenger drinks alcohol during the transport	1	0%	Substance consumption ↑

+ New COUNT 5

Continents

To promote: Continents for which scientific studies in the database give trends that on average align with your selection.
 To avoid: Continents for which scientific studies in the database give trends that on average oppose to your selection.

☑ To promote ☑ To avoid

Continent name	Description	Studies	Conflict
🌎 North America	Vehicle deployed in North America	61	32%
🇪🇺 Europe	Vehicle deployed in Europe	37	34%
🌏 Oceania	Vehicle deployed in Oceania	6	28%
🌏 Asia	Vehicle deployed in Asia	3	38%

Interpreting the Advices

The Advices page contains three sections: Advices on Usages, on Continents, and on Mode of Use. For each of these sections, you can select two tabs:

- "To promote" means that these are the recommendations to follow to respect your strategy.
- "To avoid" means that these are the recommendations to avoid to respect your strategy.

For each advice, you will find three attributes:

- The Experts or Studies attribute corresponds to the number of experts and the number of studies used for the calculation, respectively.
- The Conflict attribute reflects a possible consensus (close to 0%) or non-consensus (close to 100%).
- The Impact attribute reminds you of your selections in the strategy tab that led to this calculation.

Impact Guesser mode

Principle

The Impact Guesser mode is designed for those who have a concept of an autonomous vehicle that they want to test for its potential long-term impacts. The tool calculates a list of impacts corresponding to your concept.

Access the Impact Guesser mode

To access the Impact Guesser mode, click on the left button (in purple) located below the sentence "What are the potential impacts of your concept?"

Navigation in Impact Guesser mode

The Impact Guesser mode consists of two main pages and two secondary pages. The main pages are:

- The Scenario page where you can define your autonomous vehicle concept
- The Impacts page where the tool calculates the possible long-term impacts of your scenario

The secondary pages are:

- The Existing Scenario page where you can select an existing concept for inspiration
- The Interpretation Help page which allows you to calculate general scores based on 19 different impact themes.

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The screenshot displays two overlapping windows from the AutoVision 1.7 / Scenario application. The top window is titled 'Usages' and contains a list of six usage scenarios, each with a corresponding image and a 'Selected' checkbox. The bottom window is titled 'Mode of use' and contains a table of usage modes with checkboxes and descriptions. Below the table is a 'Continent of deployment' section with a similar table.

Usages

The selection of usages makes it possible to calculate qualitative social impacts.

Usage selection Usage selection (picture)

Context Subject

- The vehicle picks up passengers and there is no one inside
- The vehicle picks up an object without a passenger
- The vehicle delivers an object without a passenger
- The vehicle goes to a cleaning center to be cleaned without a passenger
- The vehicle finds a parking spot and parks there without a passenger
- The passenger works during the transport

Mode of use

The selection of modes of use allows for the calculation of quantitative socio-economic and environmental impacts.

Mode of use selection

Scenario	Mode of use	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Not specified	Mode of use not specified in scientific studies used to calculate impacts
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Shared (car-sharing)	The vehicle does not belong to the user, but they do not share the ride with other people (operating similarly to a taxi)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Shared (ride-sharing)	Shared use in carpooling (for example, a small autonomous shuttle)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Private	The person uses their own vehicle, which they do not share

+ New

Continent of deployment

The selection of continents allows for the calculation of quantitative socio-economic and environmental impacts.

Continent selection

Scenario	Selected	Continent name	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not specified	Not specified in the studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Oceania	Vehicle deployed in Oceania
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Asia	Vehicle deployed in Asia
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	North America	Vehicle deployed in North America
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Europe	Vehicle deployed in Europe

+ New

?

Defining a scenario

To define a scenario, simply select usages, modes of use, and deployment continents.

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Defining a scenario using an existing concept

By clicking on the "Be inspired by an existing scenario" button at the top right, you can select an existing concept. This selection is then reflected on the Scenario page with the appearance of a "🎬" symbol in front of each usage, mode of use or continent indicating that they correspond to the chosen existing scenario.

Calculating impacts

Once your scenario is defined, you can calculate impacts by clicking on the button at the bottom right: "GUESS IMPACTS".

Interpreting qualitative social impacts

Social impacts appear first on the Impacts page. Impacts are listed by theme. For each theme, the following are distinguished:

- The trend: this is the possible evolution calculated by the tool
- The intensity: this is the average level of intensity with which this impact will be experienced (1 = low, 10 = high)
- The experts: this is the number of experts concerned by this calculation
- The conflict accounts for any possible consensus (close to 0%) or lack thereof (close to 100%)

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The screenshot displays the 'Quantitative impacts' section of the AutoVision 1.7 software. The interface is organized into a sidebar on the left and a main content area. The sidebar includes a search icon, a list of impact categories (Distance, Energy, Environment, Parking), and a 'New' button. The main content area shows a detailed view for each category, including a table of impact indicators with columns for 'Evolution value', 'Studies', and 'Conflict'. A 'COUNT' label is positioned below each category's table. A help icon (question mark) is located in the bottom right corner of the window.

Quantitative impacts

These **quantitative** socio-economic and environmental impacts are calculated exclusively using the selected **modes of use and continents**.

► Understanding columns

☰ Impacts

▼ Distance 2 ... +

Indicateur d'impact	Evolution value	Studies	Conflict	...
➤ Total mileage	0%	30	28%	
➤ Mileage per person	17%	1	0%	

+ New

COUNT 2

▼ Energy 1 ... +

Indicateur d'impact	Evolution value	Studies	Conflict	...
➤ Energy consumption	-66%	2	20%	

+ New

COUNT 1

▼ Environment 2 ... +

Indicateur d'impact	Evolution value	Studies	Conflict	...
➤ CO2 emissions	-22%	2	13%	
➤ Greenhouse gas emissions	-50%	2	42%	

+ New

COUNT 2

▼ Parking 1 ... +

Indicateur d'impact	Evolution value	Studies	Conflict	...
➤ Parking space required	-86%	8	16%	

+ New

COUNT 1

Interpreting quantitative socio-economic and environmental impacts

Social impacts appear second on the Impacts page. Impacts are listed by theme. For each impact, the following are distinguished:

- Evolution value: This is a weighted average made among all scientific studies.
- Studies: This is the number of scientific studies used for the calculation.
- Conflict reports a possible consensus (close to 0%) or not (close to 100%).

Going further with the interpretation help

The "Interpretation Help" button at the top right of the Impacts page provides average scores for the 19 impact themes of the tool. The calculation rule for these scores can be modified if necessary (click on "arbitrary grid").

Caution with results

Inconsistent effect

When you choose many different inputs, some may have a bigger effect on the final result. This happens because more experts or studies have focused on those inputs. But just because many experts have studied something doesn't mean it'll have more chance of happening in the future.

No interaction between the models

The SMI and RUI models do not interact with each other. This means that choosing an usage will not change the quantitative socio-economic, or environmental impacts at the end. Also, choosing a validity domain will not change the qualitative social impacts at the end.